

QUIZ

LAST NAME: Nyero
FIRST NAME: Richard
PROGRAM CODE: ACA-401
COURSE CODE : PHGH
PERIOD NUMBER: 6
INSTRUCTOR: Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes).
The author did use Zotero to insert references.
The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which one of the followings best represent the starting point of writing essay?
 - Initial response to the topic or question.¹
 - Write down everything you know about the topic.
 - Analyzing and answering everything concerning the essay.
 - Identifying key words and clarifying the approach.
2. Presenting essay is one of the necessities in academic profession, which one of the followings are vital in essay writing?
 - Reading and writing.
 - Reading and referencing.
 - Researching and writing.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck, and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*, 3rd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 14-15.

Deleted: .

Formatted: Justified

Reading and researching.²

3. **In writing an essay, a student needs to structure the essay systematically to communicate the idea as follows.**

Introduction, The body, and Conclusion.³

Introduction, Summary, the body, and conclusion.

Summary, the body, and conclusion.

Summary, the body, and conclusion.

4. **The followings define plagiarism, except.**

When someone uses source of information and give credit to the author.

Taking someone else words and ideas without crediting or referencing the person.

When someone uses source of information and give credit to the author.⁴

Direct copying and pasting from the internet and giving credit to the author.

When someone uses source of information without giving credit to the author.

5. **Which one of the followings describe the rule of thumb for writing papers?**

State the main thesis, stay focus, write clearly, make the writing interesting, support assertion, do not plagiarize.

² Laurent Cleenewerck, and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1, 2*.

³ Ibid, 3.

⁴ Ibid, 4.

Deleted: .

Deleted: 3rd ed. (Bangui Euclid University, 2021), 14-15), 2....

Formatted: Font: Italic

- Take the views seriously, state the main theses, stay focus, write clearly, make the writing interesting, support assertion, and do not plagiarize.
- Do not make the writing boring and clumsy, take the views you are discussing seriously, state the main theses, stay focus, write clearly, make the writing interesting, support the assertion, and do not plagiarize.
- All the above.**⁵
6. **There are two kind of research problem, which one of the followings are the two main research problem?**
- Theoretical and practical problem.
- Theoretical and conceptual problem.
- Practical and conceptual problem.**⁶
- Practical and operational problem.
7. **Research can either be pure or applied, which one of the followings describe pure research?**
- When the research addresses conceptual problem.
- When the research addresses theoretical problem.
- When the research addresses conceptual problem that have practical consequences.**⁷
- When the research improves understanding of the community.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck, and Kabiru Gulma., *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, 14-15*.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press editorial staff. 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Press), 29.

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 30.

Deleted: 3rd ed. (Bangui Euclid University, 2021), 14-15.

Formatted: Font: Italic

Formatted: Justified

Deleted: w

Formatted: Font: Italic

8. **In research, we look for data to test hypothesis and develop argument, which one of the followings are data sources in research?**

- Publish books, journal, and registers.
- Published books, primary and tertiary.
- Primary, secondary, and tertiary.**⁸
- Primary, secondary, and published book.

9. **Which one of the following is the recommended order in Turabian Authors –date citation style of book by a single author?**

- Reason and evidence.**⁹
- Claim and reason.
- Acknowledgement and response.
- Response and evidence.

10. **In social science, there are qualitative and quantitative research approaches that should be chosen, which one of the followings are directly tied to choosing qualitative research approach?**

- Research hypothesis and claim.
- Research questions and problem statement.
- Research problem and purpose.**¹⁰
- Research problem and hypothesis.

⁸Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 35.

⁹Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 58-59.

¹⁰Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 33.

Deleted: Manual for writers, 35.

Formatted: Font: Italic

Deleted: Manual for writers, 58-59.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 3rd ed. Bangui Euclid University, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press editorial staff. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

World Health Organization. *Style-Guide Global Health*. World Health Organization Headquarters: World 2nd ed. Health Organization, 2013.

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

Deleted: <#>Which one of the followings describes qualitative research approach?[¶]
 Describing current condition and investigating relationship and study cause effect.[¶]
Promoting deep understanding of the social settings as viewed from the perspective of the research participants.^{11¶}
 Implies descriptive, study cause effect phenomena investigation.[¶]
 Involves complex process of data collection and analysis.[¶]
Which of the followings is the reason for engaging the participants as active collaboration in qualitative research inquiry?[¶]
 To provide a platform for research participants for their voices to be heard.[¶]
 To bring about change in social structure and process.[¶]
 To create a political debate and discussion that empower participants to take actions.[¶]
To avoid marginalizing the participants as a result of the research inquiry.^{12¶}
The following are the strategies or tradition of inquiry in qualitative research approach “except”[¶]
 Case study and ethnography.[¶]
 Ground theory and phenomenology.[¶]
Observation and content specific.^{13¶}
 Hermeneutics and narrative.[¶]
In literature review, which of the followings years of published books should be considered?[¶]
 6-12 years.[¶]
 10-15 years.[¶]
5-10 years.^{14¶}
 5-15 years.[¶]

Formatted: Font: Italic

Formatted: Justified

Commented [GK1]: Delete one period!

Formatted: Justified